

INFLUENCE OF MONEY SCARCITY ON MENTAL HEALTH. AMONG MIDDLE-AGED ADULTS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Scarcity of money is characterised by the lack of access to physical cash due to the enforcement of a cashless policy, has emerged as a significant social issue in Nigeria. This qualitative research aimed to examine the influence of money scarcity on the mental health of middle-aged adults in Akwa Ibom State. The study utilized the Basic Psychological Need Theory (BPNT) and employed a qualitative research design, gathering primary data from participants through a structured In-depth Interview Guide. The study comprised middle-aged adults aged 36 to 60, with respondents selected using a purposive sampling technique. The data collected were analysed through thematic analysis. The results indicated a positive association between money scarcity and the mental health of middle-aged adults in Akwa-Ibom State, Nigeria. Additionally, it was found that mental health issues such as anxiety and frustration among middle-aged adults have been exacerbated by money scarcity. The findings suggest that provision should be made on other means to store money, other than banks. And male and female adults should be trained to manage and store their resources through those created avenues, not limited to banks.

Keywords: Money scarcity, mental health, and middle-aged adults

INTRODUCTION

The mental health status of middle-aged adults exhibits significant regional variations. For instance, individuals in Germany, South Korea, and Mexico have reported enhancements in their mental well-being (PsyNet, 2021). Conversely, in nations such as the United States and Australia, middle-aged individuals have indicated a higher prevalence of depressive symptoms compared to their older counterparts (Technology Network, 2021). These discrepancies underscore the necessity of this study, which aims to explore the mental health of middle-aged individuals in Akwa-Ibom State and the factors influencing it. According to an article by Heels Care Network (2022), mental disorders typically arise in response to specific triggers. These triggers can emerge unexpectedly, resulting in a disruption that leaves the individual feeling overwhelmed, anxious, and stressed. For example, research by Han *et al.* (2021) highlighted the relationship between economic factors and mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic. Job loss significantly contributed to financial strain and heightened anxiety regarding the virus, ultimately leading many individuals into a state of depression.

A study carried out by Obadeji *et al.* (2014) revealed that the prevalence of depression, a mental health disorder, among middle-aged individuals was 23.1% greater than the figures

reported in general population studies in Nigeria. The results of such research highlight the existence of mental health disorders among middle-aged individuals, indicating that it is essential to give due attention to the factors contributing to this issue. Mental health is characterized as a condition of emotional and psychological well-being that enables individuals to cope with the stresses and anxieties of life. In more straightforward terms, it signifies the "absence of mental disorders" (WHO, 2022). Discussions surrounding mental disorders are increasingly prevalent, with approximately one billion individuals affected worldwide (United Nations, 2022). In Africa, it is estimated that around 116 million people are afflicted by mental disorders (This Day, 2022). Nigeria is among the African nations with a significant incidence of mental disorders. The Association of Psychiatrists in Nigeria (APN) reports that approximately 60 million Nigerians, out of a total population of about 200 million, are affected by mental disorders (The Association of Psychiatrists in Nigeria, 2022). These concerning statistics render this study both compelling and essential.

Money plays a vital role in individual lives. However, scarcity of money could affect mental health. Money scarcity is defined as the "shortage of supply or distribution of money in the economy with the presence of physical quantity". Meaning, money in an economy is available, but the inability to access the money becomes elusive resulting in money scarcity (Kerckhove *et al.*, 2020). Various determinants could change and shift mental health continuity. For instance, exposure to unsuitable economic, social and even environmental systems could raise the probability of people experiencing mental health disorders.

Cashless policy was introduced and implemented in Nigeria on April 1, 2012, with the aim of decreasing the circulation of physical currency within the economy. According to Odumeru (2013), the initial phase of this policy was launched in Lagos State, and to ensure the effective execution of this initiative, electronic banking was introduced, leading to the development of various mobile banking solutions, including point of sale (POS) terminals, Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), web banking, and other financial tools designed to improve financial transactions. These innovations facilitated fund transfers, bill payments, and expedited teller services, all without the necessity of physical cash (Yasin, 2017; Olanipekun *et al.*, 2013).

Recently, another policy was introduced on December 15, 2022 to replace certain Nigerian currency denominations with newly designed notes, which subsequently became legal tender with an initial deadline of 37 days (Moses-Ashike, 2023). This initiative aimed to combat money laundering in Nigeria; however, it inadvertently led to significant challenges and hardships for the populace (Morphy, 2023). The cashless policy was amended to transition the nation to a fully developed cashless economy by January 9, 2023 (Ezinwanne, 2023). Nevertheless, the implementation of this revised cashless policy resulted in a shortage of the new Naira notes, long lines at banks and ATMs, and exorbitant fees charged by POS merchants. E-banking services were also affected, with transfer delays extending over several weeks. This rapid transition resulted in a scarcity of cash. According to the Vanguard (2023), the Nigerian Medical Association (NMA) convened to address the issue of Naira scarcity. During this meeting, the NMA Chairman expressed grave concern over the "untold hardship and anguish" inflicted upon citizens due to the turmoil surrounding the cash swap policy, which has subjected individuals to both physical and mental distress. This statement underscores the importance of the study. Economic, social, and environmental factors hinder the achievement of complete mental health devoid of disorders. Reports indicate a high

prevalence of mental disorders among middle-aged individuals, raising the question of how these reported mental health issues are influenced by the scarcity of money.

Various researchers have investigated topics related to mental health and mental disorders. For example, Obadeji *et al.* (2014) conducted a study that explored the prevalence and predictors of depression among individuals residing in Nigeria. This cross-sectional survey revealed a notably high incidence of depression within the country, with 40% of the participants falling within the age range of 30 to 49 years. However, the study was limited to women, who comprised the entire sample, thereby not providing a comprehensive understanding of the mental health conditions affecting the broader population. The findings indicated a significant correlation between depression and both female gender and HIV-positive status.

Hawkins *et al.* (2020) investigated the socio-economic factors related to mental health disorders in Fort Portal, located in western Uganda. This qualitative anthropological research was carried out between January and March 2017. The findings indicated that employment status and food insecurity were the primary factors impacting mental health. It is noteworthy that the sample for the previous study comprised health workers and community leaders, thereby excluding middle-aged men and women from the community perspective. This research hereby examined the influence of financial scarcity on the mental well-being of middle-aged individuals, both male and female, aged between 35 and 60 in Akwa-Ibom State, irrespective of their employment or community status as a gap in literature.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The major objective of the study was to examine the influence of money scarcity on mental health of middle-aged adults in Akwa Ibom State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Money Scarcity and Mental Health of Middle-Aged Adults

Numerous social, economic, and environmental factors can influence mental health. Schwartz (2018) defines "money scarcity" as the insufficient total amount of money in circulation among the public at a specific time. Consequently, when an excess of money is removed from circulation, deflation occurs, and this monetary shortage can lead to depressive states (Boyle and Jackson, 2021). Robinson and Smith (2023) indicate that financial concerns heighten the likelihood of mental health disorders. In a similar vein, Richardson *et al.* (2013) assert that financial instability significantly affects mental health, as the pressures of debt and other monetary challenges can result in feelings of depression and anxiety. Soomin and Lu (2023) emphasize that one of the key indicators of an individual's mental health is their financial well-being. They further elaborate that a lack of financial stability often leads to the accumulation of loans and debt, which can induce feelings of shame and distress, ultimately exacerbating conditions such as depression, anxiety, or stress-related disorders.

Lyungqvist *et al.* (2016) indicate that poverty can result in significant psychological issues, including anxiety, insomnia, feelings of loneliness, stress, depression, and diminished self-esteem. According to Butterworth *et al.* (2009), financial difficulties stemming from unemployment, housing instability, and childhood poverty are closely associated with increased levels of depression in individuals. The deterioration of mental health hampers one's ability to manage personal tasks, as individuals may struggle to concentrate and lack the

energy to address their growing challenges (Zare *et al.*, 2013). Middle-aged adults frequently bear the burden of caregiving responsibilities, which places them under considerable pressure and emotional strain.

Money Scarcity and Mental Health Disorders in Middle-Aged Adults

Anxiety, as previously mentioned, is often linked to worrying thoughts. In certain instances, it may represent a natural reaction to stress. However, Marter (2022) notes that anxiety stemming from financial difficulties is marked by profound worry, fear, and stress regarding monetary matters, whether personal or business-related. The anxiety induced by financial strain can be particularly difficult to manage and may have enduring effects on an individual's mental well-being (Fan and Ryu, 2022).

According to Bradley *et al.* (2009), concerns about financial insufficiency can arise from various sources, including the inability to afford children's education, fears of homelessness, and food insecurity. Adults aged 35 to 60 often bear the responsibility of providing for their families or managing multiple obligations that require a stable financial foundation. Consequently, while the specific financial concerns of middle-aged adults may differ, there remains a pervasive sense of fear, worry, and stress associated with the issue of financial scarcity (Butterworth *et al.*, 2009).

Barry *et al.* (2020) assert that anxiety stemming from financial scarcity manifests in various symptoms, including insomnia due to difficulties in initiating sleep, diminished appetite, elevated blood pressure, panic attacks, migraines, and impaired concentration resulting from negative thought patterns, among others. Additionally, Marter (2022) indicates that financial-related anxiety can heighten the risk of familial dysfunction, as family members may experience conflicts arising from monetary issues, potentially leading to the disintegration of the household over time.

The financial demands associated with living expenses, nutrition, and other necessities can impose significant stress on middle-aged individuals. Concerns regarding insufficient funds can escalate, fostering feelings of hopelessness that may culminate in depression (Rowe and Gepp, 2021). Hiilamo and Grundy (2020) note that depression is characterized by symptoms such as low self-esteem, fatigue, disinterest in enjoyable activities, pervasive feelings of hopelessness, irritability, and suicidal ideation, among others.

The absence of financial resources can lead to feelings of depression among middle-aged adults, as they may experience a decline in self-esteem stemming from their inability to acquire necessary items or fulfill their responsibilities towards dependents. Research by Guan *et al.* (2022) indicates that many individuals in this age group may already be grappling with health challenges, making feelings of worthlessness particularly perilous, as they might believe they lack reasons to continue living. Coyne *et al.* (2003) highlight that individuals often turn to maladaptive coping strategies, such as excessive alcohol consumption and social withdrawal, in an attempt to escape their financial difficulties, which can further exacerbate their health issues. Moreover, at the peak of depressive episodes, Zhang *et al.* (2010) note that individuals experiencing profound despair and negative thoughts may resort to suicide. In this context, a study by Saxby and Anil (2012) confirms that financial concerns are a significant factor contributing to the suicides of various middle-aged adults aged 43, 45, 46, 48, 50, and 56.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Basic Psychological Need Theory

The Basic Psychological Needs Theory (BPNT) was introduced by Ryan and Deci in 2000. This theory is one of six mini-theories derived from the broader Self-Determination Theory. BPNT posits that the satisfaction of three fundamental needs—autonomy, competence, and relatedness—is essential for an individual's well-being. Conversely, the failure to meet these needs can lead to frustration and a significant decline in mental health, as well as distressing experiences (Vansteenkiste *et al.*, 2020).

According to BPNT, autonomy is the primary need that must be satisfied to maintain stable mental health. This need reflects the inherent human desire to have control over one's actions and decisions (Ryan and Deci, 2017). For middle-aged adults, financial constraints may hinder the fulfilment of this need, as they may lack access to their funds to meet personal requirements at their discretion. Such limitations can diminish their overall satisfaction, heighten frustration, and adversely impact their mental health and well-being.

The second requirement for fulfilment according to the basic psychological need theory (BPNT) is the need for competence. This need encompasses the perception of oneself as capable and effective, possessing the ability to achieve personal goals and meet various needs (Cantero *et al.*, 2020). Financial constraints can hinder the fulfilment of the competence need. For middle-aged adults, limited access to financial resources adversely affects their capacity to perform daily tasks, such as purchasing groceries, paying for transportation, and settling household bills. The struggle with feelings of inadequacy stemming from their inability to provide for themselves and their families may lead to significant anxiety and stress.

The third requirement identified by the basic psychological need theory (BPNT) is the need for relatedness. This need is motivated by the desire to receive care and to extend care to others, which can be fulfilled through spending time at home with family and fostering connections (Sakan *et al.*, 2020). However, financial difficulties may compel middle-aged adults to remain at home, potentially exacerbating feelings of depression, particularly if this situation is not a voluntary choice. The frustration experienced by these individuals may manifest as aggressive behaviour, which could negatively impact family dynamics. Additionally, the inability to provide for their families may lead to self-isolation among middle-aged adults, fostering feelings of worthlessness and increasing the risk of suicidal thoughts due to depression.

Frustration stemming from unfulfilled needs is considered a significant factor contributing to mental health disorders such as anxiety and depression. Consequently, the theory posits that individuals, particularly middle-aged adults, ought to proactively seek out activities and goals that foster a sense of emotional mastery and fulfilment, thereby mitigating feelings of annoyance associated with unmet needs.

METHODOLOGY

This research utilized a survey design that incorporated a qualitative methodology. The investigation was carried out in three Local Government Areas within Akwa-Ibom State: Eket, Ikot-Ekpene, and Uyo. These areas were selected based on their representation of the Senatorial Districts in Akwa-Ibom State, ensuring a diverse demographic that includes both

male and female middle-aged adults. Furthermore, these regions are characterized by the use of currency for daily transactions related to buying and selling. The study's population consisted of middle-aged adults aged 35 to 60, encompassing both genders from the aforementioned Local Government Areas. The focus on this demographic was intentional, as they are deemed most capable of providing informed opinions grounded in their personal experiences.

In alignment with the research methodology employed, the sample size was established at the point of data redundancy, also known as saturation. As noted by Benjamin et al. (2018), there are four models of saturation: theoretical, inductive thematic, priori thematic, and data saturation. This study specifically utilized the thematic saturation model, which involved identifying redundancy in the data through the researcher's judgment.

The qualitative study employed a purposive (non-probability) sampling technique. This approach allowed the researcher to exercise discretion in selecting participants who were most relevant to the research problem. The researcher specifically targeted individuals aged 35 to 60, who expressed a willingness to participate and had experienced financial difficulties. A total of 55 participants were recruited from three Local Government Areas: thirteen from Eket, seventeen from Ikot-Ekpene, and twenty-five from Uyo. It is important to note that saturation was reached within each Local Government Area. However, this sampling method lacks a purely scientific basis, as it does not provide an equal opportunity for all potential respondents to be selected.

In this study, the researcher acted as the moderator, while a Research Assistant supported the process by taking notes and providing backup audio recordings. The In-Depth Interview (IDI) method was utilized, which is a discovery-oriented approach in qualitative research aimed at gathering comprehensive insights regarding the subject matter. The objective was to explore participants' perceptions, feelings, and experiences (Guion *et al.*, 2011). This methodology facilitated a deeper understanding of the relationship between financial scarcity and mental health among middle-aged adults in the selected local government areas of Akwa-Ibom State. All in-depth interviews were recorded using an audio device, and detailed notes were maintained.

The qualitative data collected from the recordings of in-depth interviews were transcribed and subsequently analyzed utilizing the thematic analysis approach. This method of thematic analysis is a qualitative data analysis technique that involves a thorough examination of data sets to identify common themes. By employing thematic analysis, the researcher was able to focus more intently on the narratives derived from the in-depth interviews, facilitating a more effective interpretation of the meanings within the data set in alignment with the study's objectives.

RESULT

Money scarcity and mental health of middle-aged adults

The respondents expressed ample knowledge of the money scarcity issue. None of the respondents, claimed ignorance about the naira denomination change, nor did they accept unawareness towards the money scarcity problem. Thus, the following response were given:

“Yes, everybody must have heard about it, except you are not living in Nigeria. The government made decision to change naira

notes during the election period” (formal employed female, 41 years old)

Another respondent says:

“Ahh yes, I have heard ooo, I experienced it. Both the old and new naira note was not accessible” (formal employed male, 54 years old)

In addition, another respondent adds:

“Yes, I hear that they make new money” (self-employed female, 42 years old)

The respondents also reported mediums, through which they accessed funds during the period of money scarcity. The following response were given:

“I go to bank, we stand on line and I cannot collect more than N5,000, sometimes the money did not reach me” (self-employed male, 53 years old)

Another respondent shares:

“ATM and POS were means, and also a little shop I operated of buying and selling really helped me have cash at hand” (self-employed female, 45 years old)

In addition, another respondent adds:

“I use both POS and ATM to get money, but the money from POS was expensive, it even cost more than the amount of money you are buying. I also used online transfer to send money for business. But the transfer is risky because of plenty bank wahala, network been jam” (self-employed female, 44 years old).

The respondents, further shared the feelings they had accompanying inability to access funds, and the following response were given:

“I feel angry, it was annoying; your own money is kept from you, very hard to cope” (self-employed female, 41 years old)

Another respondent shares:

“It was really distressing and I felt deeply frustrated” (formal employed female, 55 years old)

In addition, another respondent adds:

“I vex, and thing be hard for house” (self-employed male, 43 years old)

The respondents gave various responses that shows they experienced symptoms or types of mental disorders, such as anxiety, stress, frustration and depression. The following

response were given:

“Yes ooo, my frustration was at a high level” (formal employed female, 36 years old)

Another respondent shares:

“Nobody really likes stress and the money situation was stressing to me” (self-employed female, 43 years old)

Another respondent adds:

“I kept thinking, how is it going to be? How is my family going to survive?” (formal employed female, 48 years old)

Still another respondent says:

“I was frustrated and frustration led to depression for me” (self-employed male, 44 years old)

Although all the respondents shared their experiences, some respondents however, explained more details on the painful memories the money scarcity issue created. Thus, the following response were given:

“Absolutely, the money problem caused me depression. I had people who begged me to help them with bulk money, and no matter how I explained that I did not have that access, they just would not understand. And also, I had to deal with angry customers who would be on the queue for hours, and would start cursing and insulting me for keeping their money from them. I have never hated my job until that time” (formal employed female, 37 years old)

Another respondent adds:

“If there was a word deeper than depression, it would be best to use it. I was really depressed. In fact, there was one day I went to the bank and stayed on queue till, we were told to leave the bank, because of closing hours and I was not able to get any money. I was supposed to go to the market that day and I did not even have transport fare, as I used the last cash when going to the bank. I stood on the road, and I don't know when I started to cry, as old as I am. I really felt like dying that day” (self-employed female, 43 years old)

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study assessed how money scarcity affect the mental health of middle-aged adults. Results have established that money scarcity affects the mental health of middle-aged adults. The response of respondents, reveal emotions influenced by money scarcity, respondents used expressions like “angry, annoying, frustrating and distressing, to describe their experience of the money scarcity issue. This finding is consistent with the findings of Richardson *et al.* (2013), who found that lack of money greatly impacts mental health, as the

anxiety of financial issues evokes negative feelings and emotion in a person.

This study findings also show that the lack of access to money by respondents, resulted in the inability to fulfil family and personal needs like provision of food and transportation, which was of importance to respondents, with responsibilities to care and provide for their family. This finding also validates the result of the study by Bradley *et al.* (2009), which shows that inability to fulfil basic needs like lack of food causes anxiety. This implies that money scarcity had a positive link with mental health of middle-aged adults in Akwa-Ibom State. The respondents' narratives on the negative feelings experienced, as well as their reports on unfulfilled needs, resulting from money scarcity, may be explained by the native idea “okuk-edi udiana Abasi”, which means- money is next to God. Thus, money is a source of happiness, comfort and well-being, as such, it should always be available. The lack of access to money, will result in unhappiness, and other negative emotions, as in the case of money scarcity.

CONCLUSION

The results of this research indicated that scarcity of money is significantly and positively associated with the mental health of middle-aged individuals in Akwa-Ibom State. Mental health issues such as anxiety, stress, frustration, and depression, which manifest through symptoms like insomnia, weight loss, and migraines, were prominently observed among these individuals, exacerbated by financial constraints. Furthermore, in alignment with the conclusions of previous studies, this research reinforces the notion that financial scarcity adversely impacts the mental well-being of middle-aged adults.

RECOMMENDATIONS

According to the research findings, the following recommendations are proposed by the researcher:

- i. Findings have shown that money scarcity affects mental health. To this end, provision should be made on other means to store money, other than banks. And male and female adults should be trained to manage and store their resources through those created avenues, not limited to banks.
- ii. As issues of mental health continues to abound, actively working help lines should be created to enable people express their frustrating thoughts to a reliable counsellor, in a bid to avoid delving into dark coping mechanisms like heavy drinking, isolation or suicide.

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